

Actas del
**XV CONGRESO
GEOLÓGICO ARGENTINO
2002**

TOMO III

Auspiciado por la Asociación Geológica Argentina

Portada: Fotografía del cerro Fitz-Roy. Foto Claudio Muñoz, 1998

XV Congreso Geológico Argentino, Actas / Cingolani, C.A.,
Cabaleri, N., Linares, E., López de Luchi, M.G., Ostera,
H.A. y Panarello, H.O. (eds).

Buenos Aires: Asociación Geológica Argentina, 2002.
xvi, 595 p.: ill.; maps; 28 cm.

ISBN 987-20190-5-3

Geology--Argentina--Natural Resources--Geomorphology--
Environmental Geology--Hydrogeology--Remote Sensing

QE231

558.2/75

XV CONGRESO GEOLÓGICO ARGENTINO

23 AL 26 DE ABRIL DE 2002, EL CALAFATE

Auspiciado por:
ASOCIACIÓN GEOLÓGICA ARGENTINA
FOMICRUZ S.E.

C.A. Cingolani, N. Cabaleri, E. Linares, M.G. López de Luchi,
H.A. Ostera y H.O. Panarello (editores)

Patrocinado por:
Repsol YPF

TOMO III

Geomorfología - Geología del Cuaternario - Glaciología - Geología Ambiental - Riesgo
Geológico - Neotectónica - Suelos - Hidrogeología - Geotermia - Geoprocesamiento
Legislación - Sensores Remotos - Ejercicio de la Profesión

Simposio: The Patagonia arc and back-arc magmas and the contribution from mantle sources

Simposio: IGCP - 471 «Evolution of western Gondwana during the late Paleozoic:
Tectonosedimentary record, palaeoclimates and biological changes»

Simposio: Fajas Plegadas y Corridas Subandinas

Simposio: Subducción Horizontal

Simposio: Primer Simposio Sobre Patrimonio Geológico y Aspectos Geológicos y Ambientales
de la Espeleología

Simposio: Medio Ambiente y Geología Urbana

Simposio: Enseñanza de las Geociencias en el siglo XXI

Simposio de Geoprocesamiento

BUENOS AIRES
2002

A GIS PROCEDURE FOR THE INCORPORATION OF GEOMORPHOLOGICAL RESOURCES AND ASSETS INTO EIA OF LINEAR INFRASTRUCTURES; A CASE STUDY IN NORTHERN SPAIN

Jaime Bonachea¹ Viola M. Bruschi¹, Alberto González¹, Juan Remondo¹ and Antonio Cendrero¹

¹DCITIMAC, Facultad de Ciencias, Universidad de Cantabria. Av. Los Castros s/n. 39005 Santander (Cantabria), España

e-mail: bonaechj@unican.es

e-mail: bruschiv@unican.es

e-mail: gonzalea@unican.es

e-mail: remondoj@unican.es

e-mail: antonio.cendrero@unican.es

Keywords: environmental impact assessment, geomorphologic assets, geomorphologic resources, GIS, northern Spain.

ABSTRACT

A proposal for the assessment of impacts on geomorphologic resources and assets is presented; it is based on the use of indicators of geomorphic effects and the criteria of performance or sustainability, as well as their translation into significant terms. Mitigation or compensation measures are also proposed. The procedure has been implemented through a GIS and applied to a case study area in northern Spain, comparing two alternatives for a new motorway. Details about the application of the procedure are given and results obtained are presented and discussed.

INTRODUCTION

Linear structures produce a series of environmental impacts, directly or indirectly determined by geomorphologic characteristics such as relief, landforms, surface materials, active processes, etc (González Alonso, 1989; Cavallin et al., 1994). Assessment of those impacts can only be carried out if the different effects of specific human actions related to construction and operation of the structures are identified, measured and evaluated in terms that allow comparisons with each other and with environmental concerns existing in the region (Beinat et al., 1999; Gómez Orea, 1999).

Geomorphic features are grouped into two categories for the analysis presented here: dynamic and static (Rivas et al., 1997, Cendrero et al., 2000). The former are processes (slope instability, erosion/sedimentation, etc) whose modification triggers a reaction of the geomorphic system and secondary effects may follow. The latter include resources or assets of value for humankind that do not significantly 'react' to human influence (surface deposits that represent exploitable resources, land units with high potential for use, high productivity or high value for conservation, visual landscape, sites of geomorphologic interest). This work deals with some of the latter elements.

General conceptual approaches for identifying and measuring impacts on geomorphologic features have been proposed (Panizza et al., 1996; Marchetti and Rivas, 2001), but no detailed methodological schemes for measurement, evaluation and integration of those impacts within a general EIA (Environmental Impact Assessment) framework have been developed. Of particular interest is the

development and testing of GIS procedures for the implementation of those schemes and their eventual incorporation into EIA practices.

STUDY AREA

The study area where the method proposed has been applied is part of the Deva valley, northern Spain (approximately 190 km² and 80,000 inhabitants). The climate is oceanic, mild and humid. The area is moderately folded and faulted. Main bedrock materials are upper Cretaceous flysch facies (calcareous and terrigenous-calcareous); some basaltic pillow lavas appear within the sedimentary sequence. Geomorphology is determined by V-shaped valleys with limited development of alluvial plains (Tamés et al., 1991). Land cover is intensely transformed; natural vegetation barely covers 16%, and only part of it are indigenous forests. Areas reforested with pine trees amount to about 60%. Built-up areas are concentrated on alluvial plain and adjacent slopes.

The project considered is a motorway linking the towns of Vitoria-Gasteiz and Eibar. Environmental concerns related to geomorphic characteristics are: a) visual impact of the new infrastructure, in rural areas with landscapes of a fairly high quality; b) land occupation or degradation in a valley where land with high potential for use is scarce; c) damage to areas of high natural value or productivity, in a zone where the extent of well-preserved natural ecosystems is limited; d) interference with natural processes and hazards, which could result in increased risks for human life or property. Possible destruction of geomorphologic resources is also considered. Two alternative routes have been analysed: A, 15 km long of which 6.5 correspond to tunnels, and B, 14.5 km long and consisting mainly of cuts and viaducts with 3 km of tunnels.

METHODOLOGY

A conceptual diagram was used to identify relationships between specific actions and significant environmental qualities and between these and environmental concerns, through chains of direct and indirect effects, for both construction and operational phases (Cendrero et al., 2000). Relevant geomorphologic interactions were thus identified; this contribution deals with some of those interactions, namely: consumable geomorphologic resources and land units with high value for conservation, productivity or potential for use.

Once specific interactions or potential impacts were identified, the following issues were considered for each one of them: indicators that can be used to measure impacts, criteria of sustainability or performance from the geomorphologic point of view, translation of impacts into significant terms, procedure for measurement/prediction, data needs, mitigation or compensation measures.

Data processing was carried out using the ILWIS 2.2 (Ilwis, 1997) GIS package. The database used was the one created for the Basque Government using GESPLAN.

CONSUMABLE GEOMORPHOLOGICAL RESOURCES

They include low-unitary-value materials: sand, gravel, clay, peat. Impacts are due to loss (construction on top or introduction of constraints for exploitation) of part of such materials. If these resources are scarce alternative, distant sources might be necessary. As sand and gravel are widely used materials, cost increases would affect all future construction activities and impact could be high.

Indicators that can be used to measure impacts are volume and monetary value of material affected. Performance from the geomorphologic point of view can be expressed using the ratio: *lost resource/reserves*; the lower its value the greater sustainability. Relevance of impacts can be assessed on the basis of the ratio: *lost*

resource/consumption rate (equivalent to years supply), or else monetary value of material affected. Data needs: maps of surface deposits, regolith thickness, built-up areas, road alternatives; also grain size of deposits, market values. The operating procedure consists of the following steps:

a). Identification of potentially exploitable deposits. Units on the 'surface deposits map' were classified according to origin; (A:alluvium, C: colluvium; K: karstic; R: artificial; Z: no deposit; E: water reservoir) and composition (gw: sorted gravel, gp: poorly sorted gravel, gm silty gravel, gc: clayey gravel, sm: silty sand, sc: clayey sand, ml: silt and very fine sand, silty-clayey sand, non-plastic clayey silt, ch: very plastic clay). Each deposit was thus labelled with a three-letter code, indicative of origin and grain size. A 'resource map' was obtained by overlay of surface deposits and built-up areas; deposits under the latter were eliminated from the analysis.

b) Volume and value determination. Overlay of 'resource' and "regolith thickness" maps was used to calculate volume of deposits; the latter includes five classes with the following average thickness (meters): 0.25, 0.75, 1.5, 2, 4. Percentage of potentially exploitable materials in each deposit was estimated using Casagrande's classification. Local market prices were used to transform percentages into monetary values. Each individual deposit and each resource type are thus characterised in terms of area, volume and monetary value (Table 1).

Table 1. Volume (m³) and value (EURO/ m³) of resource types

Type	Volume	Price	Value
<i>Sorted gravel</i>	5,028,550	3.3	16,594,215
<i>Poorly sorted gravel</i>	590,800	3.3	1,949,640
<i>Silty sand</i>	1,344,950	3.9	5,245,305
<i>Clayey sand</i>	3,516,600	5.3	18,637,980
TOTAL	10,480,900		42,427,140

c) Impact calculation. Each motorway alternative was overlain on resource map. Tunnel sectors were excluded. A 50 m strip on either side of the new structure was considered. The result (Table 2) was expressed in terms of geomorphic impact (m³ deposit affected) and significant impact (potential monetary loss).

Table 2. Comparison of resource (m³) and value (EURO) affected for two alternatives

	Total area	IMPACT Alternative A	IMPACT Alternative B
<i>VOLUME (m³)</i>	10,480,900	133,100 (1.27%)	161,600 (1.54%)
<i>VALUE (EURO)</i>	42,427,140	478,890 (1.12%)	612,460 (1.44%)

Lost resource/reserves ratio is 1.27 for alternative A and 1.54 for alternative B. It is clear that A represents a more sustainable option. The amount sterilised in the case of alternative A is equivalent to 2.38 years consumption in the area, and 2.89 years for B.

Mitigation/compensation measures include removal of deposits prior to construction or improvement of accessibility to other deposits in the area (thus reducing exploitation costs and increasing their exploitation potential).

VALUABLE LAND UNITS

These non-consumable geomorphologic resources include land units with high potential for use (UHPU), value for conservation (UHVC) or potential productivity (UHPP). The first have attributes that make them attractive for residential, commercial, industrial or other uses; UHVC have well-preserved natural land cover, valuable species or high biodiversity; UHPP have microclimate and soils favourable for farming. All such units represent scarce assets in the study area; if they are physically occupied or close to the motorway they will be destroyed or seriously degraded.

An obvious impact indicator is total area of each type of unit occupied and/or degraded by the motorway. Performance can be expressed in terms of percentage of the unit type affected; comparison with the rates of land “consumption” for different uses will also provide a measure of sustainability. Market value of land units consumed or degraded or potential productivity is a measure of relevance.

UHPU are defined by the following conditions: gradient <20%, no geotechnical limitations, not subject to natural hazards, near population centres, near roads. Maps used for identifying and mapping UHPU on the basis of those criteria (Table 3) are: *Slope gradient* (derived from DEM using 10x10 m pixel), *Geotechnical conditions* (reclassified in 4 categories: favourable, acceptable, unfavourable, very unfavourable), *Flood hazard* (return periods represented: 10, 100 y 1000 years), *Population centres* (includes all consolidated nuclei), *Road network* (includes all practicable roads).

Table 3. Criteria to define high potential for use

Class	Gradient (%)	Geotechnical conditions	Flood return period (y)	Distance to centres (m)	Distance to roads (m)
<i>High</i>	< 20	favourable, acceptable	> 1000	< 1000	< 200
<i>Low</i>	> 20	unfav., very unfav.	< 1000	> 1000	> 200

Original vector maps were transformed into raster format and processed using ILWIS; two types of units were defined for each map: high and low potential *High potential units* are those meeting all criteria established (Table 3); the rest were considered as having *low potential*. Criteria were applied using a stepwise procedure, eliminating on each map units not meeting the criterion.

Impact was determined by overlay of motorway alternatives over the UHPU map obtained. A road width of 100 m within which total loss is assumed was used. A buffer of 50 m on either side was also considered; within this buffer a correction factor of 0.5 was applied. Tunnel sectors were excluded from the analysis. Geomorphic impact is expressed as area of UHPU lost. Performance of each alternative is assessed using the ratio: UHPU affected / total UHPU area and also comparing the area lost with the rate of UHPU consumption for other activities in the area. Translation into significant terms was made computing the value of UHPU lost. The reference value used corresponds to a 2000 m² plot, flat and hazard free, less than 100 m away from a road and 200 m from the town of Vergara (360 EURO/ m²). Table 4 presents the results obtained for the alternatives analysed. Clearly alternative B is better from this point of view. Performance ratios are 0.018 and 0.012 for alternatives A and B respectively.

Table 4. UHPU affected by motorway alternatives (m²)

UHPU	Alternative A		Alternative B	
	(m ²)	% Total	(m ²)	% Total
<i>Total area before motorway</i>	5,404,400	4.38	5,404,400	4.38
<i>Area affected</i>	97,600	1.81	64,900	1.20
<i>Area in buffer</i>	48,800	0.90	32,450	0.60
<i>Monetary value (EURO)</i>	43,920,000		29,205,000	

Rates of "land consumption" for urban, infrastructure and industrial activities in northern Spain (Rivas et al, in preparation) have been estimated between 5 and 10 m²/person/year. This represents 400,000 - 800,000 m²/year in the study area, mostly in UHPU. Taking the lower figure as a reference, the effect of the motorway would be equivalent to less than one third of normal UHPU use rates in the Deva valley.

Mitigation/compensation. Attributes of some UHPU can be reproduced; if destruction of certain UHPU cannot be avoided project design should include "construction" of similar units near the new road. In the case considered compensation could be achieved constructing some 150,000 m² and 100,000 m² of UHPU for alternatives A and B, respectively.

UHVC were derived directly from the vegetation map (Alnus copses and Quercus woods on acid terrain). Mapping of UHPP was based on the following maps: *Vegetation*; (for eliminating units considered above), *Soil capability*; (reclassified into 5 categories; A: very high, B: high, C: moderate, D: low, E: very low), *Altitude*; (obtained from DEM; areas below 300 m have been considered), *Solar radiation*; derived from DEM and parameters related to solar position during the day and throughout the year (<http://aa.usno.navy.mil/data/docs/AltAz.html>, Pickering, 1990; Ilwis, 1997; Felicísimo, 1994). Altitude and solar radiation provide information on microclimatic conditions. Solar radiation was computed for the 21st of each month for year 2000, for each hour between sunrise and sunset. Average of those values has been used to characterise each pixel. The model obtained shows relative radiation in 255 classes. The upper 30% (<179) was considered as high potential.

Managed land units with high potential productivity are those meeting criteria defined (Table 5); limits were defined according to practices in the area. The rest were considered of 'low relative productivity'.

Table 5. Re-classification of variables

Class	Soil capability	Altitude (m)	Radiation (%)
<i>High</i>	A, B	< 300	30 (>179)
<i>Low</i>	C, D, E	> 300	70 (<179)

The final map obtained by overlay has therefore three classes: *natural land units with high value for conservation*, *high-productivity managed land units* and the rest (low relative productivity). Impact was measured on the basis of area of valuable or productive units affected by the alternatives considered (Table 6).

Table 6. Area affected by motorway

Units	Alternative A			Alternative B		
	(m ²)	% total	% unit type	(m ²)	% total	% unit type
<i>Valuable natural</i>	81,600	0.06	1.22	143,000	0.12	2.14
<i>Productive managed</i>	158,800	0.13	2.59	236,000	0.19	3.86

Performance of alternatives was assessed on the basis of percentage of unit type destroyed; it is worst for managed productive units and for alternative A (from this point of view). Relevance was expressed in terms of potential biomass loss. Data obtained for most common crops in the area (Gobierno Vasco, 1999) are: cultivated prairies: 3000 gr/m²/year, cereals: 420 gr/m²/year, potatoes: 1700 gr/m²/year. No determinations of productivity of natural units analysed here are available for the study area, but 2.5 m³/ha/year is a reasonable value for oak woods according to local timber companies.

Crop productivity can be expressed in monetary terms, as it refers to products with a market value; that is not the case of natural productivity. For comparison purposes only, it has been assumed that the “economic value” of natural biomass is that of wood production. Productivity of managed units (both biomass and monetary value) has been taken as the average for the above mentioned crops. Potential annual losses obtained using those assumptions are: 1700 gr/m²/year (about 3400 EURO/ha/year) for high productivity managed units and 2.5 m³/year (about 1900 EURO/ha/year) for natural valuable units (minimum value, not counting value of services performed). Those figures have been used to calculate impacts in significant terms (Table 7). The results obtained show that alternative A has a lower impact.

Table 7. Impact produced by motorway

Units	Alternative A			Alternative B		
	(Ha)	Prod./year	€/year	(Ha)	Prod./year	€/year
<i>Valuable natural</i>	8.16	20.4 m ³ /y	15504	14.30	37.5 m ³ /y	27170
<i>Productive managed</i>	15.88	269.9 t/y	53992	23.60	401.2 t/y	80240

Mitigation/compensation. Topsoil can be removed from units to be destroyed and replacing it at the end of the operation or placing it elsewhere. Mitigation or compensation for damage to UHVC requires long periods. A suitable compensation measure can be the restoration of degraded ecosystems in the area. Soil conservation and regeneration actions in other parts of the area are another compensation measures. The criterion should be to maintain or increase the total area of such systems or their natural productivity.

FINAL COMMENTS

The procedure described, based on the identification of landform units and materials, makes it possible to express impacts on geomorphological resources and assets by means of simple, quantitative indicators. On the basis of those indicators criteria of sustainability and relevance can be defined, also in quantitative terms, to facilitate comparison and integration with other impacts. These, in turn, allow the identification of suitable mitigation or compensation measures. The whole procedure is transparent and replicable and can easily be implemented on a GIS platform, thus enabling rapid analysis and comparison of alternatives.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was carried out as part of Project GETS (contract: ERBFMR CT97-0162, TMR Programme, European Commission).

REFERENCES

- Beinat, E., Bressan, M., Jones, M. and Fabbri, K.. 1999. Geographical information systems and environmental impact assessment. UNIGIS.Amsterdam.
- Cavallin, A., Marchetti, M., Panizza, M. and Soldati M.. 1994. The role of geomorphology in environmental impact assessment. *Geomorphology*, 9: 143-153.
- Cendrero, A., Bertens, J., Remondo, J., González-Díez, A., de la Pedraja, A., Giusti, C., Bruschi, V.M., Fernández, J.M., Francés, E., Otero, C., Díaz de Terán, J.R., Rivas, V., Salas, L., Bonachea, J., González-Lastra, J., González-Lastra, J.R. and Tamés, P.. 2000. An Approach for the Incorporation of Geomorphological Factors into EIA of Transportation Infrastructures; A Case Study in Northern Spain. *Int. Archives on Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing*, Vol. XXXIII; CD-7/1.
- Felicísimo, A.M. 1994. Modelos Digitales del Terreno. Introducción y aplicaciones en las ciencias ambientales. Pentalfa, Oviedo.
- Gobierno Vasco.. 1999. Anuario Estadístico del Sector Agroalimentario 1997-1998: CAPV. Departamento de Agricultura y Pesca.
- Gómez Orea, D. 1999. Evaluación del impacto ambiental. Mundi Prensa, Madrid.
- González Alonso, S. (ed.) 1989. Guía metodológica para la elaboración de estudios de impacto ambiental. 1. Carreteras y ferrocarriles. MOPU. Madrid.
- IIWIS. 1997. The Integrated Land and Water Information system, version 2.2. Software Manual. ITC, The Netherlands. <http://www.itc.nl/Iiwis>.
- Marchetti, M. and Rivas, V. (eds.) 2001. Geomorphology and environmental impact assessment. Balkema, Lisse (NL).
- Panizza, M., Fabbri, A., Marchetti, M. and Patrono, A. (eds.). 1996. Geomorphologic analysis and evaluation in environmental impact assessment. ITC Publication. No. 32.
- Pickering, G. 1990. Digital image analysis of SPOT multi-spectral data for topographic mapping. Msc. Thesis, ITC, Enschede, The Netherlands.
- Rivas, V., Rix, K., Francés, E., Cendrero, A. and Brunsten, D. 1997. Geomorphological indicators for environmental impact assessment; consumable and non-consumable geomorphological resources. *Geomorphology*, 18(3-4): 169-182.
- Tamés, P., I. Mendiola, C. Pérez, I. Ortega, A. Salazar, S. de Alba, J. Gallardo, G. Portero, M. Henar, A. Olivé, J.R. Díaz de Terán, E. Francés and A. Cendrero. 1991. Geomorfología y edafología de Guipúzcoa. Diputación Foral Guipúzcoa. S. Sebastián.